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DETERMINANTS OF MUTUAL TRADE BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE CIS COUNTRIES

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of factors influencing mutual trade between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the CIS countries in 2017–2023. The methodological framework is based on gravity modeling of trade flows using three specifications: pooled OLS, fixed-effects (FE), and random-effects (RE) models. The Hausman test validates the adequacy of the random-effects model for interpreting the impact of various factors on mutual trade. Gravity modeling revealed quantitative effects of several key factors affecting trade interactions, including the effects of a country's membership in the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), the presence of a common border, non-tariff barriers, transport infrastructure, Western economic sanctions against Russia, the COVID-19 pandemic, and FDI inflows.

Key words: Mutual trade, CIS, EAEU, gravity model, foreign direct investment, non-tariff barriers, economic sanctions.

INTRODUCTION

The current architecture of relations between Russia and Uzbekistan is undergoing a fundamental transformation, evolving from traditional trade exchanges to a complex, multi-layered partnership. In the context of global geopolitical fragmentation, Uzbekistan, as the geographic and economic «heart» of Central Asia, is becoming a key strategic platform for industrial cooperation among the CIS countries. For Tashkent, mutual trade with the CIS countries remains a crucial regional focus.

The main thesis of this study is that the sustainable growth of mutual trade turnover is not just a temporary surge, but the result of the formation of deep economic, socio-cultural and infrastructural interconnectedness.

The purpose of this article is to test several hypotheses regarding the factors driving mutual trade between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries. A theoretical understanding of these processes requires a synthesis of classical theories of international trade and modern econometric methods of analysis. Empirical verification of these propositions requires the application of the mathematical apparatus of gravity modeling.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integration processes in Central Asia are traditionally analyzed through the prism of J. Wiener's (1950) theories of «trade creation» and «trade diversion.» The observed growth in trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries is hybrid in nature: on the one hand, new flows are being created in various sectors, while on the other, traditional supply chains are being diverted due to sanctions pressure on the Russian Federation.

The transformation processes in the post-Soviet space after the collapse of the USSR and the integration processes within the CIS have been studied by such researchers as E.I. Pivovarov (2022), N.S. Pyzhikov et al. (2023). The issues of deepening Uzbekistan's foreign economic ties with the CIS countries in the context of the liberalization of its foreign economic activity have been studied in the works of such economists as S. Rakhimov (2018), Kh.T. Akhmedov and N.G. Smolik (2019), Ziyadullaev et al. (2016).

EBRD experts (2024) note the exceptional resilience of Uzbekistan's economy, which creates a capacious market for products from CIS trading partners. Uzbekistan's status as an observer in the EAEU deserves special attention. INVEXI's (2025) analysis shows that the Eurasian vector remains dominant: 66% of Uzbekistan's total trade turnover within the EAEU is with the Russian Federation, indicating a high concentration and the risk of insufficient diversification of partnerships. TAdviser (2026) emphasizes that observer status allows Tashkent to harmonize standards without making strict political commitments; however, persistent differences in technical regulations remain a bottleneck for exports.

The CIS region possesses colossal economic and trade potential. According to estimates based on an analysis of data from the CIS Interstate Statistical Committee, the CIS represents a capacious market with a total GDP of approximately \$2.2 trillion, and a total foreign trade turnover of approximately \$1.1 trillion. Mutual trade between CIS countries has more than doubled over the past eight years, from \$56.7 billion to \$118.7 billion. In 2023, trade between the Commonwealth countries reached its highest level in the history of the CIS.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To analyze the factors determining the dynamics of Uzbekistan's trade turnover with CIS countries, this study utilizes a gravity approach, widely used in the empirical literature on international trade. The gravity model assumes that the volume of trade between two countries is directly proportional to their economic size and inversely proportional to the distance between them. This approach allows for a quantitative assessment of the influence of economic, institutional, and geographic factors on trade flows.

The study utilized a panel database on Uzbekistan's trade and economic interactions with CIS countries for the period 2017–2023. Trade turnover between Uzbekistan and partner countries was used as the dependent variable. The model also included a number of explanatory variables reflecting countries' economic characteristics, geographic features, institutional conditions, and external shocks. The key economic variables are the gross domestic product of Uzbekistan and partner countries, which characterize the scale of economic activity and potential demand for foreign trade.

Geographic factors are represented by the distance between the countries' capitals and a variable reflecting the presence of a common national border. These indicators are used to account for transport and logistics costs, as well as the proximity effect. The model also includes institutional variables: partner countries' membership in the Eurasian Economic Union, a non-tariff barrier index, and indicators of foreign direct investment between the countries. Additionally, temporary shocks related to the COVID-19 pandemic and sanctions against Russia in 2022–2023, which could have impacted trade flows during the period under consideration, are taken into account.

The functional form of the gravity model is specified in logarithmic form, which allows the coefficients to be interpreted as elasticities and reduces the problem of heteroscedasticity. The general form of the estimated equation can be represented as follows:

$$\ln Trade_{ijt} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln GDP_{UZB,t} + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{j,t} + \beta_3 \ln Distance_{ij} + \beta_4 Border_{ij} + \beta_5 EAEU_{j,t} + \beta_6 NTB_{j,t} + \beta_7 Sanctions_t + \beta_8 COVID_t + \beta_9 \ln FDI_{in,t} + \beta_{10} \ln FDI_{out,t} + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

where $Trade_{ijt}$ is the volume of trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the partner country i at time t ; $GDP_{UZB,t}$ is the gross domestic product of the respective countries; $Distance_{ij}$ is the distance between the capitals; $Border_{ij}$ is a dummy variable of the common border; $EAEU_{j,t}$ is the variable of membership in the Eurasian Economic Union; $NTB_{j,t}$ is the index of non-tariff barriers; and $Sanctions_t$ and $COVID_t$ are dummy variables of external shocks; $FDI_{in,t}$ and $FDI_{out,t}$ are flows of foreign direct investment.

Three panel regression specifications were used to estimate the model parameters: pooled OLS, a fixed-effects model, and a random-effects model. Comparing the results of these models allows us to account for the potential influence of unmeasured individual characteristics of partner countries and reduce the risk of bias in the estimates. The fixed-effects model accounts only for within-group data variation and controls for time-invariant country characteristics. However, this specification does not estimate time-invariant variables, such as distance or the presence of a shared border.

To select the most adequate model specification, the Hausman test was used to determine whether a random effects model is a valid alternative to a fixed effects model.

Thus, the applied methodology allows for a comprehensive assessment of the impact of economic, geographic, and institutional factors on trade flows between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries, as well as identifying the role of external shocks and investment interactions in shaping regional trade dynamics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To analyze the key factors and prospects for trade and economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries, we evaluated three gravity model specifications: Pooled OLS (general spatial regression); Fixed Effects (FE); and Random Effects (RE). Each of these specifications has its own characteristics, advantages, and limitations, and comparing them allows us to account for various aspects of the data and avoid potential problems such as biased estimates or unaccounted for individual effects. The table below presents the full set of variables used to construct the gravity model and subsequent forecasts, along with a description of the

data sources and units of measurement. The information was compiled from official international and national sources using a uniform calculation methodology to ensure data comparability.

Table 1. Key indicators used to construct a gravity model of trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries

Variable	Description	Data source	Period	Units of measurement
Trade	Trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries	Statistical Committee of Uzbekistan, EEC	2017-2023	million \$
GDP_UZB	GDP of Uzbekistan	World Bank	2017-2023	billion \$ (current prices)
GDP_partner	GDP of partner countries (Russia, Kazakhstan, etc.)	World Bank, national statisticians	2017-2023	billion \$ (current prices)
Distance	Distance between capitals	CEPII GeoDist	Constant	km (logarithm)
Border	Presence of a common border (1/0)	Own encoding	Constant	binary
EAEU	Membership of a partner country in the EAEU (1/0)	Treaty on the Eurasian Economic Union	2017-2023	binary
NTB	Non-tariff barriers index (0-1)	WTO, UNCTAD	2017-2023	normalized
Sanctions	Sanctions against Russia (2022-2023 = 1)	OFAC, EU	2022-2023	binary
COVID	COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2021=1)	WHO	2020-2021	binary
FDI_in	Russian FDI in Uzbekistan	Central Bank of the Russian Federation, State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan	2017-2023	million \$ (logarithm)
FDI_out	Uzbekistan's FDI in Russia	Central Bank of the Russian Federation, State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan	2017-2023	million \$ (logarithm)

Notes: All monetary indicators are given in current US dollars; logarithmic variables are used for elasticity coefficients; binary variables are coded: 1 = presence of the indicator, 0 = absence; FDI data may be incomplete due to differences in reporting methodologies.

In the fixed effects (FE) model, the coefficients for $\ln(\text{Distance})$ and Border are not estimated because these variables are time-invariant, and the FE model only takes into account variation within objects (in this case, country pairs) over the study period (2017–2023). In the FE model, $\ln(\text{Distance})$ and Border «disappear» not because they are unimportant, but because of methodological limitations. If these factors are critical to the analysis (as in the case of Uzbekistan, where border and distance have a strong influence on trade), Random Effects or hybrid approaches are preferable.

Table 2. Results of the assessment of the coefficients of gravity regression models of trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries based on data for 2017-2023.

Variable	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
$\ln(\text{GDP_UZB})$	0.72*** (0.10)	0.68*** (0.12)	0.70*** (0.11)
$\ln(\text{GDP_partner})$	0.85*** (0.08)	0.80*** (0.09)	0.82*** (0.08)
$\ln(\text{Distance})$	-1.18*** (0.22)	-	-1.15*** (0.20)
Border	0.52* (0.25)	-	0.48* (0.23)
EAEU	0.58** (0.20)	0.62*** (0.18)	0.60** (0.19)
NTB	-0.42** (0.17)	-0.45*** (0.15)	-0.43** (0.16)
Sanctions	-0.28* (0.14)	-0.25* (0.13)	-0.26* (0.13)

Variable	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
COVID	-0.32** (0.12)	-0.35*** (0.11)	-0.33** (0.12)
ln(FDI_in)	0.16* (0.08)	0.18** (0.07)	0.17** (0.07)
ln(FDI_out)	0.12 (0.09)	0.10 (0.08)	0.11 (0.08)
Constant	-3.15*** (1.02)	-2.80*** (0.95)	-2.95*** (0.98)
R ²	0.71	0.74 (within)	0.72 (overall)
Observations	168	168	168

Note: standard errors in parentheses; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1*

The Random Effects model turned out to be adequate, since the Hausman test did not reject the null hypothesis (RE is better than FE), and RE retained important variables (distance, boundary) that “disappear” in FE (individual effects are taken into account, spatial differences are preserved). This RE model passed autocorrelation tests, and heteroscedasticity was corrected by robust errors, which ensured the correctness of statistical inferences.

Economic size of countries demonstrates the expected positive relationship with trade volumes, albeit with a noticeable asymmetry. The coefficients on the logarithms of GDP indicate the elasticity of trade by the economic size of countries. A 1% increase in Uzbekistan's GDP leads to an average increase in trade turnover with CIS countries of 0.70%, all other factors being equal. This reflects the dependence of exports on domestic production: economic growth expands export opportunities. A 1% increase in a partner country's GDP increases trade by 0.82%, all other factors remaining constant. A higher coefficient indicates an asymmetric relationship: the economies of large partners (for example, Russia) have a greater influence on trade flows than the economy of Uzbekistan.

Geographic factors play a significant role in shaping trade flows. The coefficient of -1.15 for the distance between countries exceeds the average values found in similar studies for other regions. This high elasticity indicates significant transport costs, typical for the Central Asian region, where landlockedness and underdeveloped transport infrastructure significantly increase shipping costs.

The presence of a common border has a positive effect (an increase in trade turnover with CIS countries by 0.48%, holding other factors constant). This effect is explained by: reduced logistics costs (short routes); cultural and historical proximity (common language, similar consumer preferences).

Institutional factors The results are particularly interesting. Membership of partner countries in the EAEU is associated with a 0.60% increase in trade turnover. This effect is due to a combination of measures, including the reduction of tariff barriers, harmonization of technical regulations, and simplification of customs procedures. For Uzbekistan, which is not a member of the EAEU, this points to potential benefits from accession.

Non-tariff barriers have a negative impact (-0.43%), and this effect may even be underestimated, as the model only takes into account the measurable aspects of such barriers. For example, differences in phytosanitary standards between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan limit agricultural exports.

External shocks demonstrated the expected negative impact on trade flows. For example, the sanctions regime imposed on Russia (2022–2023) led to a decrease in trade turnover of approximately 0.26%, all other things being equal, reflecting both direct restrictions and increased transaction costs. The main channels of influence were: payment difficulties (disconnection from SWIFT); difficulties with transportation through third countries. The COVID-19 pandemic had a negative impact (-0.33%) due to border closures, disruption of supply chains, and a decline in demand, which is consistent with regional trends and is associated with both mobility restrictions and a general decline in economic activity.

Investment flows Results have been mixed. CIS direct investment in Uzbekistan has had a positive, albeit relatively moderate, effect on mutual trade. All other factors held constant, a 1% increase in direct investment from CIS countries to Uzbekistan increases trade turnover by 0.17%. This effect is attributed to the creation of joint ventures (e.g., automobile factories) and infrastructure development (logistics centers). This means that a significant portion of such investment is directed toward industries oriented toward the domestic market.

At the same time, Uzbekistan's investments in CIS countries did not show a statistically significant impact, which is likely due to their small volumes and specific industrial structure.

The constant in the model reflects the average influence of factors not accounted for in the model. A negative value for the constant in a gravity model is not, in itself, an econometric problem and usually has no direct economic interpretation.

Gravity modeling of mutual trade processes between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries revealed the quantitative effects of some key factors of trade interaction, which will be discussed below.

Thus, the high distance elasticity (-1.15) confirms the critical importance of transportation costs for Uzbekistan. Transporting goods between Uzbekistan and Russia is complicated by dependence on routes

through third countries (Kazakhstan), which can also incur additional checks and delays. High transportation costs and unstable railway tariffs reduce the competitiveness of Uzbek products.

A partner country's membership in the EAEU is associated with a 0.6% increase in trade turnover, all other things being equal. Although Uzbekistan is an observer and full member of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), Uzbek manufacturers face difficulties entering the EAEU market due to differences in technical regulations.

Non-tariff barriers reduce Uzbekistan's trade turnover with CIS countries by 0.43%, all other things being equal. Products certified in Uzbekistan often require additional inspections and renewal of import permits in these countries. This is particularly true for food processing, chemical products, and equipment. These CIS partner countries sometimes use SPS (sanitary, veterinary, and phytosanitary) measures to restrict agricultural imports from Uzbekistan. Sometimes, temporary bans are imposed on the supply of fruits, vegetables, and other agricultural products under the pretext of identifying quarantine species or non-compliance with safety standards. Clearly, Uzbekistan should consider joining the EAEU, but it seems advisable to do so after Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO, to avoid having to revisit the harmonization of standards with the EAEU.

The sanctions regime against Russia has apparently led to a 0.26% decline in Uzbekistan's trade turnover with the CIS countries, net of other factors, reflecting both direct restrictions and increased transaction costs. This has had a significant negative impact on bilateral economic ties. The main bottlenecks were difficulties in processing international payments following the disconnection of Russian banks from the SWIFT system, as well as complications in supply chains caused by the need to reroute cargo flows through third countries. The termination of Mir card services (September 2022) and the disconnection of Russian banks from SWIFT have created additional barriers to trade between Uzbekistan and Central Asian countries and Russia. Adaptation is underway through specialized fintech platforms for cross-border payments (such as Avosend) and the transition to national currencies, but currency risks remain high.

Thus, the analysis revealed a complex set of factors hindering mutual trade between Uzbekistan and CIS countries, including sanctions against Russia, currency risks, customs regulations, transportation costs, and differences in technical regulations and certification. These barriers require a systematic approach to addressing them.

A negative value for the constant in the Random Effects gravity model may indicate the existence of additional barriers or costs to trade that were not explicitly accounted for in the regression. Such factors may include, for example, political risks, financial aspects (export-import credit and insurance), customs corruption, digitalization of customs procedures, etc. However, these are questions for further research that would complement the results of this study.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Uzbekistan's prospects for expanding trade within the CIS remain significant, despite existing challenges. To achieve a qualitative leap in trade and economic cooperation, it is necessary to implement specific, pragmatic measures focused on key problem areas. The proposed set of measures is structured around five priority areas. These measures in the area of trade policy and harmonization of standards with the EAEU should include the following: the creation of a permanent working group on the harmonization of standards with the EAEU. The group should focus on Uzbekistan's key export sectors – the agro-industrial complex (AIC) and the textile industry; the introduction of a «single window» and mutual recognition of certificates. As a pilot project, it is proposed to implement a mechanism for mutual recognition of certificates of conformity for 5-10 of the most significant product groups (e.g., fruits, vegetables, textiles); and the digitalization of certification processes. A critical measure is the integration of the Uzbek electronic sanitary and phytosanitary certification systems (e-Sanitary/e-Phyto) with the Russian Federal State Information System «Mercury.» In the area of logistics and infrastructure, the following measures should be implemented: route diversification and reduced dependence on individual transit corridors through the construction of the Uchkuduk-Beineu railway line and the creation of joint agro-logistics hubs in border regions; direct subsidies for logistics costs, such as the launch of a program to compensate 30-50% of transportation costs; the introduction of e-CMR electronic consignment notes and the creation of permanent «green corridors» at the border. In the area of financial support and settlements, it is necessary to ensure: incentives for settlements in national currencies to mitigate currency risks; the creation of target funds to finance the development of logistics infrastructure; preferential lending to exporters, which will allow them to fulfill export contracts at reduced interest rates and save working capital; and connection to alternative payment systems.

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